

Comparison of 810nm Red Diode Laser to 520nm Green Diode Laser for the Treatment of Threshold Retinopathy of Prematurity (ROP)

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Introduction

This is a sequential retrospective comparison at a tertiary level 3 perinatal center, (The Ivano-Frankivs'ka Oblasna Dyttyacha Klinichna Likarnya, Ivano-Frankivsk), in Western Ukraine. Infants included in study were transferred from other facilities.

Materials and Methods

Study compared sixty infants, two equal groups, both eyes treated over five years by a single pediatric ophthalmologist. Each infant underwent a dilated fundus examination within 48 hours of admission and received treatment within 24 hours of being diagnosed with threshold ROP, defined as stage 3 in any zone with plus disease. Both groups had comparable disease severity. Red diode laser (LightMed LIGHTLas 810nm, San Clemente, CA) was utilized from 1/2021 until 3/2023, after which green diode laser (Norlase LION 520nm, Copenhagen) was introduced. Infants were treated exclusively with laser covering the entire avascular retina; none received anti-VEGF. Post-treatment examinations were performed within 72 hours and weekly thereafter until discharge. No retreatments were required.

Results

The assessed parameters included number of laser spots, amount of energy applied and laser duration. The average number of spots placed into each eye with the red laser was 1082 (SD 381) with the green laser 2233 (SD 587). The average energy required to make an adequate laser burn with the red laser was 299mw (SD 90) and the green laser 212mw (SD 59). The duration with the red laser averaged 600ms and with the green 150ms.

Conclusion

This single-center comparison of red vs green laser treatment of ROP demonstrates green provides more burns, shorter duration, lower energy delivery, fewer eye complications compared to red laser. Introducing green laser improved post-treatment eye conditions: less retinal edema, fewer retinal hemorrhages, clearer corneas and retina view during/after procedure. Larger controlled studies are necessary to confirm findings.

Keywords

laser diode, ROP